

IMPROVING THE POSSIBILITIES OF TRAINING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR SPIRITUAL-EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON AXIOLOGICAL APPROACHES

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Abstract. *Since the emergence of the Internet, some have evaluated it positively, while others have talked about its negative aspects. The acceptable view on this topic is that the Internet is a tool like television and radio. If we use it for good, it is good, but if we use it for bad, it becomes bad. The most important factor here is the human factor. Because a person can spread both correct and incorrect information at the same time. On the other hand, students and young people can accept any good or bad information without understanding it. Therefore, an important task of teachers and mentors is to show the young generation using the Internet the right path and warn them of harmful consequences. On the other hand, it is to teach them how to avoid being influenced by individuals who promote ideas contrary to our national values on social networks.*

Keywords: *imprinting, existential pressure, imitation, identification, reflection, reflection.*

Introduction. Spiritual and educational activities are an integral part of the professional activity of a future teacher. The content, forms and methods of spiritual and educational activities are embedded in the content of social and humanitarian and general professional disciplines taught in higher educational institutions. Through social and humanitarian disciplines, students' intellectual culture is developed, and scientific and innovative thinking skills about society are formed. The practical goal of teaching social and humanitarian disciplines in higher educational institutions, based on the State Educational Standards, is to teach students to apply their acquired knowledge in practice, that is, to ensure the development of professional competencies in students.

Preparatory work for spiritual and educational activities cannot be carried out in dependence on one discipline or set of disciplines. The versatility of spiritual and educational activities imposes a number of requirements on its content. The first of such requirements is the personal qualities of the future teacher. The development of personal qualities characteristic of professional activity in students is a process that begins from the first days of pedagogical education. Students initially study the requirements of the state and society for the future teacher through specialized subjects. The pedagogical profession places such demands and tasks on future teachers that, first of all, they should be reflected in the attitude towards the student, who is the object of activity and is considered the highest value. For this, students should acquire true humanity, basic knowledge about human nature, and experience in assessing their positions in relation to life, the social environment, and existence on the basis of knowledge, observations, experiences, and conclusions acquired in disciplines, interdisciplinary, and outside higher education institutions. It is considered a social requirement to provide education and upbringing based on State educational standards, regardless of the teacher's personality, origin, race, religion, and affiliation, and to respect the student as the future of humanity. [9]

Methodology. Based on the subject-subject approach at all age stages, socialization can be interpreted as the development and self-transformation of the individual in the process of assimilation and reproduction of culture, which occurs in the interaction of a person with purposefully created living conditions for himself.

The essence of socialization, the essence of socialization is a combination of adaptation and isolation of a person in a given social environment. [1]

Adaptation (social adaptation) is the process and result of the opposing activities of the subject and the social environment (J. Piaget, R. Merton). Adaptation involves the coordination of the requirements and expectations of the social environment with his attitude and social behavior towards a person; it is the coordination of the self-assessment and claims of the individual with his capabilities and the realities of the social environment. Thus, adaptation is the process and result of the transformation of the individual into a social being.

Isolation is the process of the individual's autonomy in society. The result of this process is the need for a person to have his own views and their existence (value autonomy), the need to have his own attachments (emotional autonomy), the need and ability to independently solve issues of personal interest, to resist life situations that interfere with his self-change, self-determination, self-realization, self-affirmation (behavioral autonomy). Thus, isolation is the process and result of the formation of human individuality. [1]

Results and discussion. From the above, it follows that in the process of socialization there is an internal, completely irresolvable conflict between the degree of adaptation of a person to society and the degree of his isolation from society. In other words, effective socialization implies a certain balance of adaptation and isolation. [2]

Psychological and socio-psychological mechanisms include:

Imprinting is the fixation by a person of the properties of vital objects that affect him at the receptor and unconscious levels. Imprinting occurs mainly in infancy. However, at later age stages, any images, feelings, etc. can be imprinted.

Existential imprinting is the unconscious assimilation of language and norms of social behavior, which is mandatory in the process of interaction with significant individuals.

Imitation is following a model, an example. In this case, this is one of the ways in which a person arbitrarily and often voluntarily assimilates social experience.

Identification is the process of unconsciously identifying oneself with another person, group, model.

Reflection is an internal dialogue in which a person considers, evaluates, accepts or rejects certain values inherent in various institutions of society, family, peer group, significant individuals, etc.

Reflection can be several types of internal dialogue: with different identities of a person, with real or imaginary people, etc. With the help of reflection, a person can be formed and changed as a result of his perception and experience of reality.

It should be remembered that the media, films, television programs as a social institution (press, radio, cinema, television) affect the socialization of a person not only by transmitting certain information, but also by presenting examples of certain behaviors of book characters. The effectiveness of this influence was noted as early as the 20th century by the reformer of Western European ballet, French choreographer Jean-Georges Noverre: "Since the passions experienced by heroes are stronger and more pronounced than the passions of ordinary people, it is easier to

imitate them.” People tend to identify themselves with certain heroes, based on their age and individual characteristics, their behavior, lifestyle, etc. 25.

Education, as a relatively socially controlled socialization, differs from relatively directed socialization in that it is based on social action. The German scientist Max Weber, who introduced this concept, defined it as an action aimed at solving problems; as an action aimed at the response, behavior of partners; as an action that involves a subjective understanding of the possible behavior of people with whom a person interacts. [3].

The theories of E. Durkheim and T. Parsons have had and still have a great influence on many socialization researchers. Until now, most of them consider the individual only as an object of socialization, and socialization itself as a subject-object process (here the subject is society or its components). In a concentrated form, this approach is presented in a typical definition of socialization given in the International Dictionary of Pedagogical Terms (G. Terry Page, J.B. Thomas, Alan R. Marshall, 1987): “Socialization is the process of mastering roles, behavior in relations with the family and society, and the development of satisfactory relationships with others.

A person, as a subject of socialization, is not only an object, but, most importantly, a subject of socialization, assimilating social norms and cultural values, becoming an active, self-developing and self-expressing full-fledged member of society. [4]

The human being as a victim of unfavorable conditions of socialization In any society, the socialization of specific people takes place in various conditions characterized by the presence of certain risks that affect human development. Therefore, there are entire groups of people who are or may become objectively victims of unfavorable conditions of socialization.

About the theory of generations ...

Many people probably did not think that people from each generation have their own values, habits and unique character. In 1991, American scientists Neil Howe and William Strauss [5] studied this situation and created this theory. It says that every 20-25 years a new generation of people is born, and this theory looks like this:

The Generation of the Rich: born in 1880 - 1900.

The Great Generation, the Generation of Winners: born in 1901 - 1924.

The Silent Generation: born in 1925 - 1945.

The Baby Boomer Generation: born during the demographic explosion in 1946 - 1964.

Generation X, the unknown generation: born in 1965 - 1982.

Generation Y, millennials: born in 1982 - 1995.

Generation Z, the boomers: born in 1995 - 2010.

Generation Alpha: born in 2010 - 2025.

The time limits of these generations are relative and may differ by 5-6 years depending on the pace of industrialization and economic development in different countries, as well as socio-economic changes.

However, it is also worth noting that the digital generation has a high interest in science and technology, in particular in such areas as engineering, information technology, biomedicine, robotics and artificial intelligence. [6]

The problem of Internet addiction has been studied in educational and scientific institutions around the world since 1994. Today it is one of the "fashionable topics" in scientific psychology. Many studies have been devoted to this problem. Special attention is paid to scientific research on determining the impact of Internet addiction on the psychological, social, cultural and moral

qualities of a person, on the formation of students' skills for rational work on the Internet, on strengthening interdisciplinary integration, and on improving the legal, socio-psychological aspects of rational use of the Internet. [7]

Among foreign studies, scientific articles devoted to the study of the phenomenon of Internet addiction, K. Yang, M. Griffith, A. Goldberg, R. Davis, are noteworthy. Authors J. Grohol, D. Greenfield, K. Surratt, J. Moreixen-Martin, P. Schumacher, C. Chu and others. They explained the concept of "Internet addiction", clarified the assessment criteria and tools. The results of the research work carried out served as a basis for the development of preventive measures by many practitioners. Their work determines the current state and prospects for studying the problem. [8]

Conclusion. In this article, we have highlighted the changes that are taking place in society due to the regular use of the Internet, the characteristics that are causing isolation in the behavior of our youth. The Internet is a great achievement today, but at the same time it has harmful advantages. We should use the Internet in a necessary and limited manner so that it does not cause harm.

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